

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

D 1.4

Compilation of stakeholder targeted materials, final

Overview of dissemination material

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1. Introduction

This deliverable seeks to create an overview of available material that can be used to inform stakeholders as described in BLOOMs objectives. The deliverable was set up as a living document and was extended and updated during the course of the BLOOM project.

This final version seeks to create an overview by shortly describing relevant stakeholders, the projects goal in targeting them, and what material would be suitable to do this. This results in a framework of communication material, which was developed throughout the project until the current final production of deliverable 1.4: Compilation of stakeholder targeted material (final). The development of stakeholder targeted materials was done in collaboration with work package 6 (Dissemination) to select the most effective way in which to impact stakeholders. Among others this has taken place in the co-creation workshops. Whereas the focus of deliverable 1.3 was on stakeholder targeted material not developed by BLOOM, this deliverable 1.4 gives an overview of all stakeholder targeted material developed within the frame of the BLOOM project and which is available on the website, also after the end date of the BLOOM project.

2. Stakeholder audiences

This deliverable seeks to be comprehensive in its overview of stakeholder targeted material. All stakeholders can be allocated to one of the audiences described in this chapter. BLOOM specifically focusses on the first two categories presented. However, during collection of communication materials, the latter two categories often came up. To be complete, they were therefore included in the overview.

The reasons to influence these stakeholders differ, and therefore the content they need to be shown differs too. The following subchapters seek to define the audience categories, and the reason to inform them.

2.1. Citizens (A1)

Citizens are the civilians that together form the general public. For the context of BLOOM this specifically means adults. They create the market of the bioeconomy and biobased economy by their role as consumers. Informing citizens, and shaping their acceptance of the bioeconomy, increasing their knowledge and awareness of bioeconomy products, helps to form the market by showing the consumers why the shift to bioeconomy is important and how it affects them.

Furthermore it is relevant to explain and showcase to citizens the options and possibilities that come with the development of the bioeconomy, not only the introduction of new crops, new bio-based products and new industries, but also new perspectives such as career opportunities.

Supplying citizens with information about the bioeconomy also prevents low-fact stakeholders negatively influencing implementation of the bioeconomy. This keeps discussion, especially on ethical topics, on a common fact-based ground, away from gut feeling. Effects of influencing citizens are expected to be seen in the short term (several years).

2.2. Young citizens (A2)

In the context of BLOOM, the term young citizens refers to children and young adults that can be influenced through education. These citizens are still forming their place in society. By informing them about the possibilities and benefits that relate to the bioeconomy, they can be shaped to actively participate in the discussions and dialogues as citizens or professionals, and function as ambassadors for the bioeconomy to their fellow citizens.

The effect of influencing young citizens can be seen on a longer time scale than adult citizens. By improving acceptance of the bioeconomy at young age, a societal change over generations can be achieved.

2.3. Industrial stakeholders (Agricultural/chemical/end products) (A3)

Industrial stakeholders are the supply chain that creates the bioeconomy. It includes professional biomass production, processing and the production of intermediate and end products. Influencing of these stakeholders is mostly focussed on showing their possible impacts and presenting opportunities. Their participation is very important for the successful implementation of a bioeconomy, but not central to the BLOOM project.

2.4. Non-industrial stakeholders (Government, NGO's, CSO's, intermediate organizations, teachers) (A4)

This category gathers all organisations that influence governance of the bioeconomy: governmental departments, non-governmental organisations and lobbyists. These parties are critical in shaping the legislative and policy framework, and shape the conditions (networks, capacities, subsidies) in which a bioeconomy can thrive. Also teachers are part of this stakeholder group as they have an important role in capacity building.

3. Detail level

Communication materials can roughly be divided into five categories, going from abstract to specific information like a funnel. For each audience described in the previous chapter, different detail levels are desired. The following overview describes the abstraction levels, and how they are relevant to the audiences.

3.1. General overview (D1)

At the lowest detail level is communication material that describes what the bioeconomy is. These overviews are usually generic, and an important frame for the (young) citizens to understand why we strive towards a bioeconomy, and how it benefits them on a societal level. This level is somewhat less important for the (non-) industrial stakeholder, as they are expected to understand the general concepts.

3.2. Technical (D2)

The second detail level describes the technical specifics of the bioeconomy. Understanding the different steps and relevant processes in the value chain: growing biomass, and / or collecting side streams, the industrial conversion processes and production of (intermediate) products, which the (young) citizen knows, but which they may not necessarily recognise as products from the bioeconomy. An overview of the supply chain creates insight into the general concepts of bioeconomy presented in 3.1.

3.3. Application (D3)

The third detail level zooms in further on the choices that must be made in the bioeconomy, regarding what biomass to grow, what processes to use and how industries will utilise these resources in order to make sustainable bio-based products. It also indicates what is happening in the direct environment of the audiences, depending very much on the specific characteristics of places and regions (natural resources, knowledge and capacities, industries and investments), and the strategic choices being made by regional innovation networks (RIS3). This can be seen as application of the more descriptive materials in aforementioned detail level 3.2.

The applied knowledge is vital in participating in the ethical questions that are an inherent part of the bioeconomy, such as the food versus fuel debate and the potential use of genetically modified organisms.

3.4. Impact (D4)

Once an overview of the bioeconomy and its questions has been built, the citizen can be presented with the scope. This focuses on how much impact the bioeconomy has: what petrochemical and other products in which markets can be replaced, how much biomass would be needed, what CO₂ emission reduction or even sequestration can be reached, what would be the climate benefits, but also which new economies, new jobs, innovations and transitions are expected to occur. Quantitative information is very suitable for this detail level.

To understand this information, the material mentioned in 3.1-3.3 must be supplied first to the audiences.

3.5. Hub specific (D5)

The information presented under 3.1-3.4 is generic for the entire bioeconomy. To fully inform citizens of the impact that bioeconomy has on them, or to inform them what is happening within their own living environment, this information must be translated or adapted to a hub or regional specific context. Therefore hub specific materials have also been created with Hub network partners which reflect specific hub related content. This enables the citizen to relate to the bioeconomy and gain a deeper understanding.

4. Overview of stakeholder targeted material

4.1. Introduction

The full list of stakeholder targeted material that is available on the website is presented here. The following tables show an overview divided in several subcategories, and the links that lead to the material: Suitcase (S), Podcasts (P), Film (F), Quiz (Q), Key messages (K), Booklets (B), School Box (C), Webinars (W) and Other (O). A total overview of all the materials the level of detail and the audiences they are targeted at is given in overview Table A at the end of this section. As can be concluded from the overview BLOOM has delivered a wide range of targeted materials, targeting the four audience groups and the five levels of detail.

4.2. Bioeconomy Suitcase and Leaflet

A suitcase on bioeconomy products was one of the major findings all the hubs had in common: providing something that makes bioeconomy touchable makes participants and the broader public understand the concept better. So all partners jointly created a suitcase that includes products from all over Europe: fabric made from wood, cups made from wood and other natural resources, egg cartons made from potato starch & cellulose fibres, straws made out of apples and many more.

<i>Suitcase</i>	<i>Products</i>	<i>Link</i>
S1	Bioeconomy materials leaflet	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/bioeconomy-suitcase-leaflet/
S2	Suitcase with materials	Available at the hub partners

4.3. Podcasts

Podcasts with relevant people (among which members of the Advisory Board were produced, in which they share their vision on the bioeconomy.

<i>Podcasts</i>	<i>Interviewee</i>	<i>Link</i>
P1	Hannu Koponen	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P2	Kazimierz Murzyn	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P3	Anna Maria Fleetwood	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P4	Johan Sanders	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P5	Maciej Guzik	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P6	Martin Greimel	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
P7	Josefin Illergaard	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/

4.4. Films

From the hubs a number of films were produced, highlighting the bioeconomy regional specialisation of biomass valorisation in the hub.

<i>Film</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Link</i>
F1	Wooden Shirt	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F2	Developing Bioeconomy teaching resources	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F3	Reaching out to EU secondary students	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F4	Bioplastics from sugar beets	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F5	Do you care about the climate? Then care about the bioeconomy	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F6	Bioplastics from bacteria	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F7	Food waste to fuel	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
F8	Biohydrogen from algae	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/

4.5. Quiz

A quiz for the general public was constructed which can be run on an Ipad and can be used at exhibitions and events.

<i>Quiz</i>	<i>Link</i>
Q1	Bloom Bioeconomy Quiz https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/

4.6. Key messages and FAQ

A learning point of the hubs was that in many workshops and activities the same questions were asked - and not only in one hub, but all over Europe. So the hubs, together with work package 1 leader Wageningen Research, collected these questions and published them in a FAQ section on the website. Also, a list of Key Messages was produced, as well an Infographic, explaining bioeconomy basics and terminology.

<i>Key messages</i>	<i>Content</i>	<i>Link</i>
K1	Key messages	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/
K2	Bioeconomy infographic	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/
K3	Bioeconomy questions and answers	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-questions-and-answers/

4.7. Booklets

Two booklets originating from the Dutch hub, explaining aspects of bioeconomy to a general public were translated from Dutch into English, and one booklet was translated into Spanish.

<i>Booklets</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Link</i>
B1	Biomass for the circular economy. Everything you wanted to know about biomass, but were afraid to ask	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/
B2	Bioplastics 2020	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository
B3	Biomasa para la economía circular	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository

4.8. School Box

The BLOOM School Box is a collection of bioeconomy related teaching resources which educators can use to introduce the concept of bioeconomy in their classrooms as a trigger to raise student interest in science subjects and their awareness of important societal challenges. The basis of the BLOOM School Box are five innovative learning scenarios, created and tested in classrooms by the 20 BLOOM expert teachers from Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Israel, Poland, Portugal, Spain and Sweden.

<i>School Box</i>	<i>Entries</i>	<i>Link</i>
C1	Back to the future	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C2	Biofuel production from fruit waste	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C3	The benefits of composting	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C4	Let's talk about bioenergy and our lives	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C5	Yeast, biofuels and novel biotechnology techniques	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C6	Don't waste your waste!	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C7	Growing plastic and new life for plastic	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C8	How poop will change the world	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C9	Building a new environmental future	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C10	Examining the thermal properties of biobased building materials	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C11	Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap lab	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C12	UnPlasticised	https://bloom-

C13	Bioeconomy for a sustainable future	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C14	Stay home and learn bioeconomy	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C15	My kitchen without food waste	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C16	Bioeconomics and fruit	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C17	Copernico in bloom	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C18	Why Bioenergy?	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
C19	Sustainable development	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/

4.9. Webinars

The main goal of the outreach webinars (webinars type c, see deliverable 3.5) were to raise awareness among citizens in one field of bioeconomy. The usage of the webinar format supported the non-digital activities and allow to easily increase the number of citizens reached by the BLOOM project program, again especially in times of COVID-19.

Webinars	Title	Link
W1	Bioeconomy: biorefinery and innovative bioproducts	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series/
W2	What the tree can do	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W3	Wear what you talk, bioeconomy and textiles	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W4	Bioplastics in your daily life	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W5	Bioeconomía en nuestro día a día	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W6	De circulaire bioeconomie in ons dagelijks leven, in Emmen	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W7	Compostable! Really true?	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W8	Biologiczna ochrona roślin / Living organisms in the protection of agricultural production	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W9	Bioeconomía circular con el sector del olivar y de la industria del aceite de oliva	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series
W10	Climate change, damaged wood, falling prices: with bioeconomy out of the crisis	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-webinar-series

4.10. Other

Next to the items listed above a MOOC was prepared on how to implement bioeconomy in STEM teaching and several Gallery Walks were made for various events.

<i>Other</i>	<i>Content</i>	<i>Link</i>
O1	MOOC, Boosting bioeconomy knowledge in schools	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/mooc/
O2	Gallery Walks	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu

4.11. Overview of detail level and targeted stakeholders of all materials

Table A: Overview of the stakeholder targeted material for 4 audiences (1. Citizens, 2. Young citizens, 3. Industrial, 4. Non-industrial) on 5 detail levels (1. General, 2. Technical, 3. Application, 4. Impact, 5. Hub related)

Detail level	Audience 1 Citizens	2 Young citizens	3 Industry	4 Non-industry
1 General	P1, P6, F5, Q1, K1, K2, K3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	F5, Q1, K1, K2, K3, C1, C5, C6, C9, C13, C14, C15, C16, C17, C18, C19	P1, P3, P4, P6, K1, K2, K3, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	P1, P3, P4, P6, F2, F3, F5, K1, K2, K3, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, O1
2 Technical	P7, F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, C2, C3, C4, C5, C7, C8, C10, C11, C12	P4, P5, P7, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	P4, P5, P7, F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, O1
3 Application	S1, S2, P7, F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C8, C10, C11, C12, C14, C15, C18	P5, P7, B2, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	S1, S2, P5, P7, F1, F4, F6, F7, F8, B2, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, O1
4 Impact	P2, P6, F5, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	F5, C4, C6, C9, C12, C13, C14, C17, C18, C19	P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, F2, F3, F5, B1, B2, B3, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10
5 Hub related	S1, S2, P7, F1, F4, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, O2	F1, F4	P7, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10	S1, S2, P7, F1, F4, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, O2

5. Reflection

This document is the final version of the stakeholder targeted materials and is delivered in month 38 of the BLOOM project. During the project, the outreach activities and the production of the stakeholder targeted materials a number of findings were encountered:

- There were found to be fewer differences among target groups than anticipated. The main distinction was between professionals and citizens.
- There was found to be much difference in awareness among citizens.
- Interaction is important for determining the level of knowledge and awareness of the people, in order to be able to explain at the right level the perspective and potentials of bioeconomy
- There is a lot of interest in bioeconomy. People need very practical information - what are the applications / products - where to buy the products, etcetera
- Make the messages as simple as possible

Questions to be answered and next steps that we propose will need to be taken in order to ensure the sustainability of the project's results are:

- Where to store the material? EU platform of knowledge, findings and products?
- There is a lot of potential for re-use, how do we make sure this is reached?
- We recommend using the materials in implementation programs under the Green deal.